

The Enrolment of Indian Women in Higher Education

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R.R. Arshath

Research Scholar, Reg No: 19213161031043

Post Graduate and Research Centre

Scott Christian College (Autonomous), Nagercoil

Affiliated to M.S University, Abishekkapatti, Tirunelveli, Tamil Nadu, India

Dr. C. Selva Smiley

Assistant Professor, Post Graduate and Research Centre

Scott Christian College (Autonomous), Nagercoil

Affiliated to M.S University, Abishekkapatti, Tirunelveli, Tamil Nadu, India

Abstract

Education is an active procedure that starts from beginning; education is a mirror of the society and base of the socio-economic development. Women Education in India the stage is a considerable role in getting better livelihood standards in the country. The literacy rate of women improves the value of living both at the house and outer of the residence by encouraging and promoting education for female children. In India, the female education rate of India at 65.6% is significantly lower than the world average at 79.7%. The norms of the patriarchal culture, still throughout the 21st century, prohibit women from making up for higher study. This paper will focus on the state-wise enrolment of women in universities and colleges and analyze the women faculty-wise distribution in higher education. The women enrolment rate in Higher Education shows that perfection has happened over the years through regard to taking into consideration particular teaching as a significant part of 'Women Development. Every girl child must be given full school learning, and a long time ago to be from side to side, Women are enrolled well-timed for Higher learning as per Women's capability and interest. It is a requirement for the socio-economic improvement of women and society at large.

Introduction

Women are an indispensable part of society. Their education influence the coming generation. The development of future generations mainly depends upon the education of the women sector. As a result, women's education realizes to live an essential part in the development of people. It preserves assist each woman to teach their kids in the direction of a good manager of the family as well as a full of life associate of the culture. The children learn their conduct and behaviour at the house, with most mothers are responsible for cultivating good manners inside their children. each learned woman can run their house healthy and create it a heaven on earth. all well-read women can believe healthy about their future and her plan in living and then choose the suitable focus, which resolves be there valuable to women throughout their life. In an independent system, the situation of women is identical to that of men. Nowadays, women are also conscious of their rights and obligations.

Objectives

1. To know about the State-wise women Enrolment in Universities and Colleges.
2. To analyze the Faculty – wise distribution of women enrolment in Higher Education.

Methodology

The study is based on a descriptive design. To study the Women Enrolment status in Higher Education, the secondary data was collected from UGC Annual Report. State-wise Women enrolment in Universities and Colleges in 2015-16, Faculty-wise distribution of Women Enrolment in Higher Education 2015-16.

Data Analysis

Enrolment of Women in Universities and College.

The act of putting yourself on to the official list of members of a course, college (or) university. The below table explains the women's enrolment of Universities and colleges.

Table 1 State-wise Enrolment of Women in Universities and Colleges in comparison to Total Enrolment: 2015-16

Sl.No	State	Total Enrolment	Women Enrolment	Percentage of women
1	Andaman & Nicobar Islands	6349	3445	54.26
2	Andhra Pradesh	1295329	555765	42.91
3	Arunachal Pradesh	32802	15979	48.71
4	Assam	485656	237795	48.96
5	Bihar	1364218	570024	41.78
6	Chandigarh	68456	37843	55.28
7	Chhattisgarh	395424	194254	49.13
8	Dadra & Nagar Haveli	5333	2521	47.27
9	Daman & Diu	3057	1206	39.45
10	Delhi	348338	170099	48.83
11	Goa	31208	18820	60.31
12	Gujarat	1398646	576879	41.25
13	Haryana	666936	318434	47.75
14	Himachal Pradesh	195361	105591	54.05
15	Jammu and Kashmir	233091	125761	53.95
16	Jharkhand	521601	252323	48.37
17	Karnataka	1557353	773561	49.67
18	Kerala	643822	378021	58.72
19	Lakshadweep	501	351	70.06
20	Madhya Pradesh	1527607	655231	42.89
21	Maharashtra	3055164	1386677	45.39
22	Manipur	92932	46337	49.86
23	Meghalaya	60730	30925	50.92
24	Mizoram	18710	9006	48.13

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25	Nagaland	29716	15410	51.86
26	Odisha	777231	370757	47.70
27	Puducherry	53362	27643	51.80
28	Punjab	734839	376847	51.28
29	Rajasthan	1563395	721466	46.15
30	Sikkim	17867	8507	47.61
31	Tamil Nadu	2375377	1239802	52.19
32	Telangana	1206873	554780	45.97
33	Tripura	61327	26012	42.42
34	Uttar Pradesh	5748990	2759167	47.99
35	Uttarakhand	330829	159063	48.08
36	West Bengal	1576316	739449	46.91
	Grand Total	28484746	13465751	47.27

Source: UGC Annual Report 2015-16

Table 1 shows that Enrolment of Women out of Total Enrolment is highest in the Union Territory Lakshadweep (70.06%) and the state of Goa (60.31%) and the lowest in Daman & Diu (39.45%).

Women Enrolment Faculty - Wise 2015-2016

Women enrolment faculty explain the number of women works in all the colleges and universities. The below table explains the enrolment of Women Faculty.

Table 2 Women Enrolment Faculty - Wise 2015-2016

S. No.	Faculty	Women Enrolment	Percentage to Total Enrolment
1	Arts/Oriental Learning	5539097	41.13
2	Science	2685403	19.94
3	Commerce / Management	2141673	15.91
4	Education	680953	5.06
5	Engineering / Technology	1360021	10.10
6	Medicine	676162	5.02
7	Agriculture	65640	0.49
8	Veterinary Science	9879	0.07
9	Law	159216	1.18
10	Others	147707	1.10
	Total	13465751	100.00

Source: UGC Annual Report 2015-16, New Delhi.

Table 2 shows the highest enrolment of women is under the faculty of Arts/Oriental Learning and with lowest in the faculty of Law, Agriculture & Veterinary Science.

Conclusion

The enrolment rate of women in Higher Education clearly shows that improvement has happened over the years with regards to considering specialized education as an essential part of 'Women Development.' Society at large both at the rural and the urban level will have to understand that today women constitute 48% of the total population, and if this 48% is debarred from attaining specialized skill, knowledge and develop calibre to deliver their best, an enormous amount of Human Resource will go waste and this will ultimately act as a major hurdle in the development of the nation. Every girl child must be given complete school education, and once that is through, she is enrolled timely for Higher Education as per her competence and interest. It is a pre-requisite for the socio-economic development of women and society at huge. completely meaningful with the intention of the competent Human Resource is necessary for the growth of the national Government and related Ministries are trying level most excellent to afford plenty of opportunities for Higher learning to Young India.

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